

Mapping from a Human Autonomic System to a Bio-Inspired Autonomic Computing Model

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Abstract—Although inspired by the biological aspect, the concept of autonomic computing is emblematic of the diversity of solutions that propose a self-governance of systems from high-level objectives. From the human point of view, the autonomic nervous system has as a central point the direct intervention of a small region of the brain called the hypothalamus. This article seeks to discuss the concept of computational autonomy from an analysis of the human autonomic system, addressing its internal functioning, in order to propose a correlated computational model that can be applied. Finally, the bio-inspired computational model is mapped to an approach for knowledge-based systems aimed at its applicability.

- Context Awareness Design
- Self-similarity Design Principle
- Adaptive Design
- Knowledge-Based Design

This position focuses on the mapping of the human nervous system principles into a computational model based on Inspired Living Systems Design. Thus, to better understand this model, the present paper gathers in section 2 some considerations regarding the functioning of the autonomic nervous system with the goal of presenting an overview, in section 3, a computational model is proposed that reports about possible features of a correlate model to the human system. In Section 4, is presented a relation between the model based on Living Inspired Design Systems and Knowledge-Based Design.

I. INTRODUCTION

Particularly, regarding life support or homeostasis, the portion of the central nervous system that controls the majority of a biological organisms visceral functions is called the human autonomic nervous system. This system helps to control blood pressure, body temperature, sweating, and other activities in a complete or partial manner, but without any conscious intervention of the brain [1].

As the center of the autonomic nervous system there is the presence of a small region of the brain called hypothalamus, which has the function of being the main integrating center of activities executed by the visceral organs.

The hypothalamus is what can be called the intermediate agent of the brain, responsible for translating emotions into physical responses. This prepares the body for quick action that may eventually be necessary [3].

If human emotions could be correlated to specific patterns of information that can alter the functional aspect of a system, the formulation of a computational model that can feel the imminent changes in order to reflect a desirable or projected state becomes interesting as an autonomous control strategy.

In general, autonomic systems can be based on [9]:

- Living Systems Inspired Design
- Policy-Based Design

II. HUMAN AUTONOMOUS SYSTEM – AN BRIEF OVERVIEW

The autonomic nervous system refers to the set of nerve elements that controls the function of the viscera. This is a system that will control the said involuntary functions, such as those of smooth muscles, cardiac muscles, glands or the viscera in general, innervating all of these structures.

Its important to note that, according to [3], some authors do not consider this system autonomous, because it closely interrelates with the central nervous system, thus, It properly receives the name of the nervous system controller of visceral function.

The autonomic nervous system consists of two separate systems that work in equilibrium, but with functions opposite in most actions, in general. These systems are the sympathetic adrenal system, which works in adaptive, emergencial, situations and the parasympathetic system which operates in a more conservative and protective way [3].

There is an interesting difference of the autonomic nervous system in relation to the somatic nervous system (which controls the striated skeletal muscles, for example), the presence of neurons outside the central nervous system that are grouped into dilations named ganglia [2].

The integration of the central nervous system with neural control system occurs at the level of visceral cortex, hypothalamus and medullary reticular formation. Particularly, the hypothalamus is the major center of integration between the two systems [3].

Belonging to the limbic system, the action of the hypothalamus is critical for regulatory functions over the affective attitude and adjustment of the body's orientation to emotions, through other systems.

III. CORRELATING THE HUMAN MODEL TO THE COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

In computing, the autonomic principles are based on the ability of a computer system to be self-governing from high level goals provided by its administrators [7]. In the human body the regulating metabolic processes represents as much as a stream of matter as well as energy into and out of the organism.

So that there might be the possibility of carrying or mobilizing matter, there is a need for an expenditure of energy. In turn, for the energy expense, there is the need for adequate information so that the system can release the energy [3].

The dependence of the regulating action to an information flow is also called a steady state, whose main feature is to adapt to variations in the environment. Just as the human body, the definition of high-level objectives in a computer system leads, somehow, to a change of balance in its inner workings.

It can be argued that the autonomic principle demands, in most cases, a relentless pursuit of strategies that can also ensure the maintenance of a projected state. In this case, the autonomic intervention results in activity of a set of actions or decisions that support the configuration which is supposed to be the ideal state.

In the human body, according to [2], the emotional states are translated by the human limbic system into actions that seek to prepare the body to different situations. This can be argued as one way of anticipation. According to [6], the term anticipation is the cornerstone of proactive computing.

To truly proactive systems, the use of techniques of statistical reasoning and data manipulation are prerequisites for systems that can quickly deal with real world situations and provide an appropriate level of interaction with users.

According [4], the area of autonomic anticipation represents an area of recent research. The same opinion is shared by [8] who shows a trend of study on autonomic computing aiming at the property of self-healing through an analysis of real-time data in order to predict future problems.

Correlating a human model to a computing model, the figure 1 suggests a model of autonomic control based on biological characteristics.

As in the human body, the flow of information from the most of visceral fibers drives pulses that do not become conscious.

Fig. 1. Model for Bio-Inspired Autonomic Controller.

For example, continually there are impulses arriving at our central nervous system that inform about the blood pressure and oxygen content of the blood, without we, however, being able to perceive them [2].

In this model, a conscious afference refers to a data set that involves the environment in which the controlled system is inserted. For unconscious afference, the collected data refer to the internal environment of the system, which represents, in a way, their visceral units.

In the biological model, the presence of ganglia, or groups of neurons, also allows for a more specific activation of viscera according to the different types of actions planned, either adaptive or protective as well as reflective.

In the proposed model, there are two types of autonomic behavior transducers, the emotional transducer which aims to predict a given risk detected in the external medium and an adaptive transducer that aims to correct abnormal situations to the internal environment of the system being controlled.

During the operation of a computer system, depending on the amount of variables involved, the autonomic challenge, so to speak, does not just mean finding a way to translate a set of data that represents a state A observed in a set of interventions that lead to another state B operating desirable.

There is a natural concern, given the unpredictable nature of many situations, in preventing the undesirable state A from being set, ie, there must also be interventions over the lifetime of a system so that any attempt to a bad change be previously canceled.

In this situation, the artificial hypothalamus proposed function is to react to interventions that mimic the sympathetic and parasympathetic pathways in the human body to respond in emergency or adaptative actions depending on the case.

IV. RELATION BETWEEN THE MODEL BASED ON LIVING SYSTEMS INSPIRED DESIGN AND KNOWLEDGE-BASED DESIGN

This approach based on the human nervous system follows the pattern Living Systems Inspired Design [9]. The computational mapping presented in the previous section can also be mapped as Knowledge-Based Design.

To construct this mapping we need to understand how the Living Systems Inspired Design works concerning the adap-

tation in relation to amendment of the managed environment. This adaptation to environmental disturbance can be used [9]:

- 1) Short-term changes – This adaptation allows the biological system to respond to a stimulus immediately: For example, an environmental temperature change moves the body temperature variable to an unacceptable value. This rapidly induces an autonomic response in the (human) organism, that is, either perspiring to dissipate heat or shivering to generate heat. Such adaptation is quickly achieved and reversed.
- 2) Somatic changes – Prolonged exposure to environmental temperature change results in the impact of the change being absorbed by the organism, that is, acclimatization. Such change is slower to achieve and is reversible once the individual is no longer in that specific environment.
- 3) Genotypic changes – A species adapts to change by shifting the range of some variables, for example, in a cold climate a species may grow thicker fur. Such genotypic change is recorded at a cellular level and becomes hereditary and irreversible in the lifetime of the individual.

With these concepts presented, you can build a high-level model based on Knowledge-Based Design (Figure 2). To do this we use two modules based on short-term (analysis based in current state) and somatic changes (analysis based in managed system history).

Fig. 2. Model for Autonomic Controller based on Knowledge-Based Design.

Note the similarity between Figure 1 and 2, which corresponds to Knowledge-Based Design. In Figure 2 the control plane receives two analyzes: one based on the case history of the managed environment - promoting learning and reasoning - and another based on the current analysis of the network - promoting an efficient solution to the current state.

The current analysis of the network can not be performed on-the-fly due to time requirements [10]. On the other hand, a solution based on historical can not adapt to the current situation due to low similarity. The ideal is to merge these approaches towards a solution close to the optimal solution and response time doable.

V. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Particularly, there is an inclination of autonomic computing to deal with the so-called soft computing, area of computing that is closest in modeling biological processes more consistently than other traditional techniques, since it deals with problems related to vagueness, uncertainty and approximations [5].

The prediction techniques refer to different analysis mechanisms, such as using statistical or probabilistic advance, as well as techniques that are based on simulation or machine learning [4]. This project is interested in these approaches as a strategy to create a bio-inspired autonomic model.

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